

A Comprehensive Review of Herbal Lipstick for Lipcare

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Abstract:- The most common beautifying ingredient added to cosmetics to enhance the beauty of lips is lipstick. A critical sum of shades, oils, waxes and emollients are utilized in lipsticks, a sort of cosmetics item that includes colour, surface, and lip assurance. Lipstick is made with excipients from a assortment of normal sources. Visit utilization of counterfeit lipstick colours can have genuine side impacts, counting cancer, skin break out, skin disturbance, and discolouration. Plant based plant extricates can be utilized to reduce side impacts. The kind, definition strategy, extraction of different colour of colours, characteristic oil, taste, physical appraisal, quality control, moulds, and lipstick imperfections are all secured in this survey of lipstick. Makeup are utilized to upgrade the see of the face. The demand for natural cosmetics is currently rising daily and is an initiable natural gift. These days, women employ a variety of natural products. Plant cosmetics, as opposed to synthetic ones, must be for human health. Because of their high activity and comparatively low adverse effects when combined with synthetic ingredients, these compositions are based on herbs that consistently garner a lot of attention. Beauty products that give advantageous qualities, such improving skin texture and making appearance more appealing, are referred to as natural cosmetics. [1]

Keywords:- Lipstick, Herbal, Beauty Products.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics are materials applied to the human body to improve its look. Skin care products such as lotions, creams, powders, perfumes, lipstick, nail polish for the fingers and toes, eye and facial makeup, permanent waves, coloured contact lenses, hair colour, gels and sprays, deodorants, baby products, bath oils, bubble baths, bath salts, butters, and many others items are highly sought after in both developed and developing nations. [benett, 1983][2]

The term “herbal” denotes safety as opposed to “synthetic”, which is harmful to human health. Consumer have taken to using herbal preparation such as pills, herbal tonics, herbal paste, herbal shampoo, herbal sindur, herbal contraception and herbal lipstick. Herbal medications are the fastest growing market for treating a variety of illnesses. Its possible that herbal users want to take charge of their medical requirement. Due to the increased negative effects of accessible synthetic preparations, many people may find the

extensive personal healthcare system unaffordable and resort to herbal medicine [kaul et al, 2010 Dwivedi et al., 2008][3]

A fatty foundation made of an appropriate mixture of oils, fats, and waxes that have been appropriately scented is used to dissolve or disperse colouring pigments, which are often produced as moulded sticks [4-6]

Lipstick are cosmetics that give lips colour, texture, and protection. They are made of pigments, oils, waxes and emollients. Only a few hues of lipsticks were available in the early 20th century. Throughout the 1800s and 1900s, dark red was one of the most often used hues.[7]

➤ Objective and Scope:

The reviews primary goal is to present a through and organized summary of the literature on herbal lipsticks, with an emphasis on the following topic:[8]

The various natural ingredients used in the formulation of herbal lipstick, such as oils, waxes, pigments, minerals, and plant extract.

The properties and benefits for the lips, such as moisturizing, healing, coloring. Antioxidants, anti inflammatory, etc.[9]

The various method and techniques used in the preparation and evaluation of herbal lipstick and the various parameters and methods of evaluation, including colour, texture, pH, melting point, breaking point, surface anomalies, aging, perfume stability, colour, texture, and more.[10]

➤ Types of Lipstick:[11-14]

Depending on the consistency, the solid lipstick is presented in ways that are lipstick stick, lipstick pencil, lipstick cream and liquid lipstick. Depending on the how much the secondary function, lipstick are classified as;

- Moisturizing lipstick
- Lipstick Nutritive
- Lipstick Hygiene or treatment lipstick
- Mattel has gloss and glitter and thick consistency.
- Satin are semi-opaque, have a slight stain sheen, are well pigmented and the texture is slightly silky.
- Long lasting lipstick
- Colourless lipstick

➤ *Lipstick Standard Qualities* : [15]

- It must not cause inflammation and be safe.
- It should give the application area a consistent colour.
- Soft lips should be made by celia.

- Under environmental condition.
- It must be easy to use the container.
- Complete livestock release is required.

➤ *The Natural Ingredients*: [16-17]

Table 1 The Natural Ingredients

Base	Oils	Flavouring Agents
Cocoa Butter	Coconut Oil	Strawberry
Bees Wax	Olive Oil	Orange
Carnauba Wax	Castor Oil	Saffron
Candelilla wax	Glycerine	Raspberry
Avocado Butter	Arachis Oil	Vanilla
Olive Wax	Grapes seed oil	Rose oil
Olive Butter	Sesame oil	Cherry
Raspberry Butter	Corn Oil	Sandalwood

II. DISCUSSION

Women’s use of cosmetics has increased dramatically during the past few decades. But only recently have the risks passed by these compounds gained attention. Formulating a lipsticks with herbal elements in the hopes of reducing the negative effects caused by the available synthetic ones was the goal of the current study on the development and evaluation of herbal lipstick.

III. CONCLUSION

The review emphasizes the increasing shift towards natural and herbal lipstick as a safer and more beneficial alternative to synthetic formulation. While traditional lipstick contain various chemical components that can lead to adverse effect such as skin irritation, discoloration, and potential long-term health risks, herbal lipsticks utilize plant-based ingredients to mitigate these concern.

The rising demand for natural cosmetics reflects consumers, preference for safer, more sustainable beauty products. This trend underscores the need for further researches and development in herbal lipstick formulation.

Ultimately, natural and herbal lipsticks represent a promising innovation in the cosmetic industry, aligning with modern preference for eco-friendly and health-conscious beauty solution.

REFERENCES

[1]. Kumar VA, Dhanaraju MD. A review on Herbal Lipstick. Journal of pharmaceutical Advanced research 2021 (4) 1179-90

[2]. Benette, w. (1983), Benette’s Cosmetics Formulary Second edition chemical publishing company, New York 90-100

[3]. Dwivedi summet and kaul Shefali, (2008) Ethno medicinal uses of some plants species by ethnic and rural people Indore district of MP Pharmaceuticals Review, 6(3)

[4]. Mehta RM pharmaceuticals-I Edn 2, Vallabh Prakashan, Delhi 2015, 2/3 -2/4

[5]. Mithal 3M. Saha RN. A Handbook of cosmetics Edn. Vallabh Prakashan. Delhi 2007, 39-47

[6]. Berg R. Kroeneke A. Beauty. The new Basics workman publishing company. New York, 2001, 1-10

[7]. Forman-Brunell M. Girihood in America. An Encyclopedia. Edn I Volume VII Santa Barbara, California, 2001, 206-217

[8]. Ahrori, f, Ramezani, N; Kikuchi, T; Yasukawa K, Tokuda, H; Masters, E, J and Manosroi, J (2010)

[9]. Akishia, T; Kojima, N. Ahmadi , Z and Mohmmodipour, H.S (2003)

[10]. Kadu M. Vishwasa S, Singh S. Review on Natural Lip Balm. Int J Res Cosmet Sci, 2015; 5(1) : 1-7

[11]. Indian Standard (IS) (1990) Lipstick (pcd) 19 cosmetic

[12]. Balsam MS. Sagarin E. Cosmetic Science and technology, 2nd ed. New York; Wiley International science publication 2008 pp-209-512

[13]. Deshmukh S, Chavan M. Sugar M. Singh S Preparation and Evaluation of natural lipstick from Bixa orella seeds Int. J Pharmabio Sci. 2013; 4; 139-144

[14]. Harry RG. Wikinson JB. Harry’s Cosmetology 6th et. London; Leonard Hill books and interest publisher; 1973’

[15]. Mawazi, S.M; Azreen Redail, N.AB Othman, N; Aloyum.S.O lipstick History, Formualtion and production; A Narrative Review, cosmetic 2022; 9:25

[16]. Chaudhary G, Goyal S. Poonia P. Lausonina inermits Linnacus. A phytopharmacological review int. J. Pharma su drug 2010: 2: 91-98

[17]. Pandey S. Meshya N. Viral D. Herbs plays an important role in the field of cosmetics int. J. Pharma Tech 2010; 2: 632-639

[18]. Mittal B.M And Saha R.N. (2003), Handbook of cosmetics 1st Ed. A Vallabh Prakashan

[19]. Sharma PP (2005) Cosmetics Formulation and quality control, 3rd ed. Vandana Publication.